

High contrast, fast chemical imaging by coherent Raman scattering using a self-synchronized two-color fiber laser

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Abstract

Coherent Raman scattering (CRS) microscopy is widely recognized as a powerful tool for tackling biomedical problems based on its chemically-specific label-free contrast, high spatial and spectral resolution, and high sensitivity. However, the clinical translation of CRS imaging technologies has long been hindered by traditional solid-state lasers with environmentally-sensitive operations and large footprints. Ultrafast fiber lasers can potentially overcome these shortcomings, but have not yet been fully exploited for CRS imaging, because previous implementations suffer from a high intensity noise, a narrow tuning range and a low power, resulting in low image qualities and slow imaging speeds. Here, we present a novel high-power self-synchronized two-color pulsed fiber laser that provides excellent performances on the intensity stability (50 dB better), timing jitter (24.3 fs), average power fluctuation (<0.5%), modulation depth (>20 dB) and pulse width variation (<1.8%) over an extended wavenumber range (2700 – 3550 cm^{-1}). Its versatility enables, for the first time, high contrast, fast CRS imaging without complicated noise reduction by applying balanced detection schemes. These abilities are demonstrated in this work by imaging a wide range of species such as living human cells and mouse arterial tissues, as well as multimodal nonlinear imaging of mouse tail, kidney and brain tissue sections by utilizing second-harmonic generation and two-photon excited fluorescence — providing multiple optical contrast mechanisms simultaneously and maximizing the gathered information content in biological visualization and medical diagnosis. This work also establishes a general scenario for remodeling existing lasers into synchronized two-color lasers, and thus promotes a wider popularization and application of CRS imaging technologies.

Introduction

Optical imaging techniques have long served as important tools for biomedical applications¹. Among them, coherent Raman scattering (CRS), which encompasses coherent anti-Stokes Raman scattering (CARS)² and stimulated Raman scattering (SRS)³⁻⁶, as well as other nonlinear optical processes⁷⁻¹³ have been successful applied for tackling biomedical problems by providing chemically-specific, label-free contrast, high spectral and spatial resolution, and high sensitivity. CRS microscopy, in particular, enables minimally invasive and continuous live imaging of biomolecular samples^{14,15}, where fluorescent molecules cannot be applied or their use might interfere with the biological applications due to the size, weight and toxicity of fluorophores; and where the bleaching of fluorophores as well as the phototoxicity of the excitation light often prevents long-term imaging or disturbs the natural behavior of biological samples. The clinical translation of CRS imaging technologies, however, has largely been stalled by the high cost and bulkiness of conventional laser sources. Standard solid-state lasers, typically Ti:sapphire lasers and synchronously-pumped optical parametric oscillators (OPOs) using free-space optics, usually have to be mounted on vibration-isolated optical tables, which creates a major technical obstacle for clinical applications. This is all the more true for CRS imaging that requires two coherent pulsed laser sources with sufficient power and low intensity noise at two different wavelengths covering a suitable range of probed wavenumbers, which must also be tightly synchronized and have matched pulse widths for generating an optimal CRS signal. Finally, both pulsed laser sources have to be temporally and spatially overlapped, on sub-picosecond time and nanometer length scales, respectively, while the stabilities in both domains should also be granted with high reliability.

To this end, various two-color pulsed fiber lasers have recently been proposed and demonstrated for CRS imaging, including fiber-Ti:sapphire hybrid sources^{16,17}, and all-fiber lasers based on processes, such as active synchronization^{18,19}, parametric wavelength conversion^{20–23}, soliton self-frequency shift^{24–29}, and supercontinuum (SC) light generation^{30–35}, to name a few. These approaches, however, have specific limitations, respectively, either high cost, low power or high intensity noise — the major challenge for directly demodulating the weak SRS signal (on the order of $10^{-4} - 10^{-6}$)⁴, see **Supplementary Material 1**. As a result, so far, there is still no entirely fiber-based coherent two-color pulsed laser source available that provides sufficiently high power and low intensity noise for fast SRS imaging without balanced detection — a technology for suppressing laser noise that requires delicate adjustments of balanced receivers to subtract the exceeding intensity noise; however, it is difficult to maintain the performance of balanced detection across a wide spectral range for dynamic samples and could also increase the complexity and cost of an imaging system.

Recent developments in advanced fiber optics have created new opportunities for generating high quality ultrafast laser pulses and have expanded their application potentials^{36–39}, such as: **1)** heavy doping of active fibers that enables high output power per unit length, up to hundreds of milliwatt from a centimeter-long active fiber^{40,41}; **2)** designing of double-cladding fibers (DCFs)^{42,43} that allows efficient cladding pumping based on cost-effective multimode fiber-coupled pump laser diodes (MMFPLDs), and creates a brightness orders of magnitude higher than the core pumping scheme⁴⁴; **3)** fiber chirped-pulse amplification (FCPA) technology⁴⁵ that further boosts the energy and thus the peak power of ultrashort laser pulses by eliminating the detrimental pulse distortion, mainly arising from fiber nonlinearities; **4)** last but not least, fabricating of multifunctional hybrid fiber components that reduces the overall complexity of

ultrafast fiber lasers and enhances their robustness^{46,47}. By leveraging these advanced fiber optic technologies, we present a novel high-power, low-noise, self-synchronized two-color pulsed fiber laser system utilizing coherent wavelength generation (CWG) through cross-phase modulation (XPM)⁴⁸. With this system we demonstrate high quality CARS and SRS imaging, along with other nonlinear imaging modalities, without the need for balanced detection, which is otherwise required to cancel laser noise in SRS imaging^{32,35}, enabling high scan speeds while keeping the complexity of the detection setup low.

Results

Different from prior realizations of the synchronized pulse generation typically seeded by noise²⁰⁻³⁵, here the synchronization between the two-color pulsed laser beams is based on the CWG in the fashion of a passive- and self-stabilization scheme. **Fig. 1a** depicts the configuration of the self-synchronized two-color pulsed fiber laser source with further details provided in **Supplementary Material 2**. The laser system starts from a passively mode-locked fs fiber laser at 1.0 μm wavelength, named the master laser. The laser cavity consists of a short piece of ytterbium-doped fiber (Yb), a drop-in polarization controller (PC) and a fiber-based optically integrated module (OIM) that provides polarization-sensitive isolation, pump/signal multiplexing and signal extraction. Passive mode-locking is realized by the nonlinear polarization rotation (NPR), a reliable technique for generating self-starting and stable fs pulses in the all-normal dispersion regime⁴⁹. The output pulse train has an average power of ~ 20 mW and a fundamental repetition rate (FRR) of 80 MHz. Such a high FRR can, in particular, enable a fast modulation of pulse intensities necessary for high speed SRS imaging. Its output is split into two parts by utilizing a 50:50 fiber optic coupler (OC), which feeds the Stokes and pump beam branches,

respectively. A system trigger signal is generated by using a photodiode (PD) that receives a leaked beam from the master laser.

For the Stokes beam generation, 50% of the fs pulse generated at 1.0 μm wavelength is amplified by using an FCPA scheme. To this end, the fs pulses are first linearly chirped in a single-mode fiber (SMF, 50 m), after which the chirped pulses are pre-amplified by a core-pumped Yb-doped fiber amplifier (YDFA). The pulses are subsequently modulated by a 20 MHz sinusoidal waveform through an in-line fiber-coupled intensity modulator (FIM), which enables an intensity modulation depth of >20 dB. The average power of the chirped pulses is further amplified to >1.0 W by a double-cladding YDFA (DC-YDFA) that is cladding-pumped by a cost-effective MMFPLD. The amplified laser beam is launched into the free space through a fiber collimator (FC1) for pulse compression. The pulse compressor, the black dotted rectangle in **Fig. 1a**, is composed of a grating (G) pair⁵⁰ and an optical telescope (L1 and L2). A slit is placed at the focal plane of L1 to perform narrowband spectral filtering.

The remaining power of the master fs laser is injected into the CWG oscillator, highlighted by the purple dotted rectangle in **Fig. 1a**, for generating stable self-synchronized laser pulses at 1.5 μm that are ultimately utilized as the pump beam for CRS imaging. The CWG oscillator constructed with an erbium-doped fiber (Er) has a similar structure as that of the master laser cavity, except that an additional wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM) coupler is used to receive the external injection. Without the external injection, the CWG oscillator operates in the quasi-continuous wave (CW) regime. Once the 1.0 μm laser beam is injected, the CWG oscillator is forced to generate a stable ps pulse train that is stably self-synchronized with the Stokes beam when the cavity length mismatch is less than 200 μm — resulting from a combined effect of the NPR pulse compression, XPM and chromatic dispersion (top middle inset of **Fig.**

1a). Briefly, the injected signal pulse initiates a pulsed perturbation on the quasi-CW laser beam at 1.5 μm through the XPM. This perturbation self-evolves into a stable pulse through the NPR compression and circulates in the cavity. The subsequent optical collision between the circulating 1.5 μm pulses and the continuously-injected 1.0 μm pulses induces a timing-dependent frequency shift to the 1.5 μm pulse train also through the XPM effect^{51–53}. If the 1.5 μm pulse train is slower than the 1.0 μm pulse train, the center wavelength of the 1.5 μm pulse train is blue-shifted, which thus increases its group velocity in the anomalous dispersion regime. On the contrary, a red-shifted center wavelength will decrease the group velocity of the 1.5 μm pulse train and force it to synchronize with the 1.0 μm pulse train when it is faster than the 1.0 μm pulses. **Figs. 1b–e** illustrate the temporal evolution of the 1.5 μm pulse train without and with self-synchronization, in the cases that the round-trip time (the inverse of FRR) of the 1.5 μm pulse is slower (**Figs. 1b,c**) or faster (**Figs. 1d,e**) than that of the 1.0 μm pulse. The timing reference is 0 s, i.e., the time when the 1.0 μm pulses are injected (not shown). Detailed studies of the self-synchronization and its versatile performance are covered in **Supplementary Material 3** and **4**, respectively. The synchronized laser pulse train at 1.5 μm is then amplified to about 1 W by a double-cladding erbium/ytterbium-doped fiber amplifier (DC-EDFA). Here, the FCPA is not utilized since ps pulses are less sensitive to the fiber nonlinearities than fs pulses in the Stokes beam. To match with the optimal wavelength window of commonly-used high quality microscope objective lenses, i.e., the Olympus UPLSAPO 60XW in this case, and highest sensitivity of the Si photodiode, i.e., typically $<1.0 \mu\text{m}$, the optical wavelength of the amplified 1.5 μm pulse train is frequency-doubled to the visible regime by the second-harmonic generation (SHG) in a periodically poled lithium niobate (PPLN) crystal.

Figure 2 shows the spectral performance of the two-color pulsed fiber laser. The center wavelength of the master fs laser can be coarsely tuned between 1010 nm and 1060 nm (**Fig. 2a**), with a bandwidth of about 8.0 nm defined by the intracavity filter (F1). A fine spectral tuning, i.e., **Fig. 2b**, is obtained by translating the slit in the pulse compressor, which enables a continuous wavelength scan with an effective bandwidth of about 1.0 nm. On the other hand, the center wavelength of the CWG oscillator can be continuously fine-tuned from 1540 nm to 1590 nm with a bandwidth of <1.0 nm (**Fig. 2c**). **Fig. 2d** showcases a typical SHG spectrum that is frequency-doubled from 1578 nm and has a spectral width of 0.35 nm, corresponding to a transform-limited Gaussian pulse width of 2.6 ps. The average power of the pump beam after the SHG crystal is >160 mW, sufficient for CRS imaging^{32,35}. It should be noted that an SHG output power of >1 W can potentially be obtained by further optimizing the SHG efficiency of the PPLN crystal⁵⁴. Current two-color pulsed fiber laser can cover a broad range of Raman resonances in the high wavenumber region, from 2700 to 3550 cm^{-1} , including the CH_2 stretching resonance at 2845 cm^{-1} predominantly associated with lipids as well as the resonance of cellular proteins at 2920 cm^{-1} . To demonstrate hyperspectral CRS capability, the SRS spectra of standard samples, such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and methanol, are measured using this fiber laser source and compared to spontaneous Raman spectra (**Fig. 2e**).

Figure 3a depicts the real-time pulse trains of the pump and Stokes beams, as measured by a 20 GHz real-time oscilloscope, while extended pulse trains up to 500 μs are also shown in **Fig. S6**. The uniform intensities over the long real-time pulse trains indicate a low intensity fluctuation, which is crucial for high quality SRS imaging³². The benefit of the fiber-based intensity modulation for SRS imaging is presented in **Fig. 3b**, which shows a modulation depth of more than 99%. This is also confirmed by the radio frequency (RF) spectrum measurement (**Fig. S7**),

exhibiting a signal-to-noise (SNR) ratio of 67 dB at 20 MHz. This all-fiber modulation scheme with large modulation depth is well suited for the lock-in detection of SRS signals and is a powerful alternative to cost intensive free-space acousto- or electro-optic modulation (AOM/EOM) schemes. The pulse widths of both pump and Stokes beams are measured to be about 2.7 ps and 3.2 ps, respectively, as shown in **Fig. 3c**, providing a reasonable compromise between signal strength and molecular sensitivity. Notably, unlike standard OPO-based two-color lasers that suffer from a large variation in pulse width when their wavelengths are tuned across a wide range in hyperspectral CRS experiments, our two-color fiber laser exhibits a constant pulse width over the tuning range, i.e., 3.2 ± 0.06 ps, corresponding to a variation of only 1.8%, which is crucial for a high fidelity of the obtained spectral data.

Since the modulation transfer from the Stokes to the pump beam in SRS is very weak, the noise performance of laser sources is a critical parameter, which, so far, has required the use of balanced detection schemes when fiber-based laser sources were utilized^{32,35}. The noise performance of our two-color pulsed fiber laser is studied on both short- and long-term time scales. To evaluate the power stability over a long time period, usually of concern for the long-term imaging of biological samples, the average powers of the pump and Stokes beams are set to about 100 mW and 550 mW, respectively, and then monitored over 100 minutes (Fig. 3d). **Within such a long time period (i.e., 100 minutes), there is a power increase of 0.2% in the pump beam and a power decrease of 1.6% in the Stokes beam; while the root-mean-square fluctuations of the optical power are only 0.1% and 0.5% for the pump and Stokes beams, respectively.** The timing jitter between pump and Stokes pulses is estimated from the intensity fluctuation of a sum-frequency generation (SFG) signal obtained by focusing the beams into a beta barium borate (BBO) crystal⁵⁵. **Fig. 3e** shows the optical cross-correlation trace measured by precisely

scanning the delay between the pump and Stokes beams, while the gray and black curves are the SFG intensities monitored over 10 seconds at two different delays, i.e., 0 ps (peak) and 2 ps (half maximum), respectively. The timing jitter is thus calculated from the intensity fluctuation of the SFG signal and the slope of the cross-correlation trace to be about 24.3 fs, i.e., $\sim 0.8\%$ of the pulse width. The relative intensity noise (RIN) of the two-color beams is also characterized and compared with a standard solid-state fs laser (Spectra-Physics MaiTai) and a typical SC-based fiber laser (**Fig. 3f**). At the modulation frequency for SRS imaging, i.e., 20 MHz, the pump and Stokes beams of our fiber laser have similar noise levels, i.e., about -147 dBc/Hz and -148 dBc/Hz, respectively. Please note that this performance distinguishes this laser source from other designs, where one of the two-color beams usually suffers from degraded noise performance after the nonlinear conversion processes^{56,57}, see **Supplementary Material 6**. Here, these two-color beams exhibit equally low RINs, since the RIN of the pump beam has been improved by 50 dB compared with previous implementations (**Table 1**) — a key requirement for high quality SRS imaging without the need for balanced detection^{32,35}. It is noted that the intensity noise level of our laser system still performs worse than standard solid-state lasers (**Fig. 3f**), the origin of which can be attributed to the pump laser noise, amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise and environmental fluctuation. It could, however, be further improved by using electronic feedback schemes⁵⁸. Currently, the entire fiber laser system is loosely placed on an optical table at a footprint of about $80 \times 85 \text{ cm}^2$ where no particular efforts trying to minimize its size have been taken, yet.

After spatial and temporal overlapping of the pump and Stokes beams using a dichroic mirror (DM) and an optical delay line (DL), the combined beams are coupled into our custom-built laser scanning microscope, see **Methods** and **Fig. S1**. To demonstrate the unique capabilities of our

two-color pulsed fiber laser, we simultaneously acquired CARS and SRS images of biological samples ranging from single cells to tissue sections. **Figs. 4a–d** show CARS and SRS images of living human osteosarcoma (U2OS) cells (**Figs. 4a,b**) and living differentiating primary myoblast (PMD) cells (**Figs. 4c,d**). Please note that no averaging was applied to any of the images of the current manuscript. Here, the CH₂ stretching mode at 2845 cm⁻¹ is utilized as the chemical contrast to mainly highlight lipid rich regions within the cells such as lipid droplets, which can be observed as areas of high signal intensity (i.e., bright spots indicated by select arrows). For the U2OS sample, the focal powers of the pump and Stokes beams were set to 33 mW and 74 mW, respectively, while maintaining a pixel dwell time of 12.5 μs (see **Table S5**) and a time constant of 2 μs for the lock-in amplifier (LIA). It should, again, be noted that these images were acquired without balanced detection for noise cancellation, demonstrating that our two-color pulsed fiber laser facilitates high contrast and fast live-cell imaging at a pixel dwell time of a few μs. In **Supplementary Videos S1** and **S2**, additional z-scans of the U2OS cells are shown (both CARS and SRS). Next, we imaged living PMD cells (**Figs. 4c,d**), which have lower lipid content than the U2OS cells. Even though the focal power was decreased to 25 mW and 47 mW for the pump and Stokes beams, respectively, lipid droplets (indicated by the arrows) and the plasma membrane highlighted by the 2845 cm⁻¹ resonance can easily be identified (**Figs. 4c** and **d**). Compared with the SRS images, the contribution of non-resonant signal results in a higher overall signal in the CARS imaging. The SRS images with SNR of 45.7 and 16.7 for **Fig. 4b** and **d**, respectively, on the other hand, specifically highlights those chemical compartments, as indicated by the white dotted circles, that are resonantly responding to the corresponding Raman resonance, which is predominantly associated with aliphatic CH₂ groups in lipids.

We also imaged tissue sections of a 2-month-old mouse with severe combined immunodeficiency. **Fig. 5** shows CARS images and the corresponding SRS images of a cross-section of superior vena cava tissue, prepared on a thin glass cover slip using a cryo microtome. **Fig. 5a** displays a bright-field image of the mouse tissue section, captured at 4x magnification. Here, the superior vena cava can be identified in the middle of the image. Two regions of interest (ROIs) are chosen for CRS imaging, as depicted by the red (ROI 1) and green (ROI 2) dashed rectangles, where multiple CRS images were taken. The sequentially acquired images are stitched together in order to extend the field of view (FOV) and provide a wider context of the sample's morphology. In **Figs. 5b** and **c**, such an extended FOV can be seen at ROI 1. Here, we observe the change from tunica media to tunica intima, as well as a thrombus containing red blood cells that are attached to the vascular wall. The yellow inset provides an enlarged view of the area of the red blood cells. **Figs. 5d** and **e** show a lipid rich area of the tunica media in the same acquisition mode. The line profile (green) across the tunica media (**Fig. 5f**) shows the intensity profiles of the CARS and SRS images and is normalized to the maximum intensity present in the line scan. Indicated by the two red arrows, we observe regions in which the non-resonant background masks small features in the CARS image that can be revealed in the SRS image due to the enhanced chemical sensitivity. In **Supplementary Videos S3** and **S4**, we utilize the z stage to move the focus through the sample at a step size of 4 μm , for CARS and SRS imaging, respectively.

The versatility of our laser source is also demonstrated by the fact that the Stokes beam after the FCPA stage can be used as an fs laser by removing the filtering slit to serve as a source for SHG as well as two-photon excited fluorescence imaging. Its central wavelength is set to 1025 nm with 8 nm bandwidth, corresponding to a pulse width of ~ 200 fs. To demonstrate this, an

unstained mouse tail tissue section was imaged by the SHG with different polarization states of the laser, while one particular polarization is shown in **Fig. 6a**. The SHG signal is mostly generated by collagen in the tendon tissue, while the signal from the surrounding muscle tissue is relatively weak. We then imaged fluorescently stained samples such as a tissue section of a mouse kidney and the neurons of a mouse brain section (**Figs. 6b–e**). In **Fig. 6b**, the fluorescence emission of Alexa Fluor 568 phalloidin shows the filamentous actin cytoskeleton prevalent in the glomeruli and brush border, while in **Fig. 6c**, the fluorescence signal of Alexa Fluor 488 (staining wheat germ agglutinin) indicates glomeruli and convoluted tubules. These two images were separated with two bandpass filters, which are centered at 519 nm and 600 nm, respectively. **Figs. 6d** and **e** are two-photon excited fluorescence images of a 200- μm thick mouse brain tissue sample prepared between two glass slides where the mouse expresses the yellow fluorescent protein (YFP) in layer-V pyramidal neurons (Thy1-YFP H-line)⁵⁹. Here, the same objective lens (Olympus UPLSAPO 60XW) is utilized to perform a z-scan of the sample over a depth range of 145 μm while using a step size of 1.0 μm (**Fig. 6d**). **Fig. 6e** shows a single frame illustrating the neuron distribution. It should be pointed out that the imaging depth is limited to the sample thickness and working distance of the objective lens (~ 280 μm). Hence, the laser source has multimodal imaging capabilities, especially because the fundamental wavelength (1570 nm) used as the pump beam for CRS imaging in this work is a potential source for three-photon excited fluorescence, which is not shown in this work.

Conclusions and discussion

We have demonstrated a ps two-color fiber laser that operates with low noise, sufficient power, and wide wavelength tunability in the high wavenumber region, from 2700 to 3550 cm^{-1} , commonly-used for CRS microscopy. Thanks to the coherent wavelength generation utilizing

cross-phase modulation, both, pump and Stokes beams display very low relative intensity fluctuations of less than -140 dBc/Hz, which enabled us to use this compact and robust laser source for performing high speed SRS imaging without balanced detection. This improvement is significant for successfully translating CRS and related nonlinear optical imaging technologies towards clinical applications, while prior implementations required either long signal integration time or balanced detection to eliminate the exceeding laser noise. As a result, we obtained high contrast, fast scanning CRS images of living human cells and mouse superior vena cava tissue. Furthermore, as an additional benefit from the fs chirped-pulse amplification in the Stokes beam branch, we were able to utilize multiple optical contrast mechanisms simultaneously by conducting multimodal nonlinear optical imaging, including CARS, SRS, SHG and two-photon fluorescence excitation. It is anticipated that the remarkably low noise of this two-color pulsed fiber laser system in both, the short- and long-term time domains, is essential for achieving high image quality of living samples at low pixel dwell times, e.g., living cells and organisms. This scheme can be extended to other wavelength windows through the same CWG method, e.g., 900 nm (neodymium-doped fiber), 1100 – 1500 nm (bismuth-doped fiber) and 1700 – 2000 nm (thulium-doped fiber). The fiber-based laser beam delivery is also compatible with many other optical imaging systems, e.g., it can easily be attached to any confocal microscope with suitable detectors and integrated with existing endoscopy systems^{60,61} through fiber connections in order to realize compact and user-friendly CRS-imaging for use in surgery and diagnostics⁶².

The current implementation can potentially be upgraded in the following two aspects: 1) for fast spectroscopic imaging, the wavenumber tuning speed can be largely increased by replacing the existing spectral filters with electronically controlled all-fiber Fabry-Pérot filters that can easily operate at speeds of >100 kHz and have widely been used to build fast wavelength-swept laser

sources for high speed optical coherence tomography⁶³; 2) to fully utilize the appealing advantages of fiber lasers for flexible beam delivery, the frequency doubling of the pump beam, that is currently performed in the free space, can be replaced with a fiber-integrated PPLN module⁶⁴, resulting in an even more compact and robust system.

Methods

Customized laser scanning microscope. Two xy-scanning galvanometric mirrors (Cambridge Technology 6215H) raster scan the laser focus across the sample. A 60x water immersion objective lens (Olympus UPLSAPO 60XW, NA = 1.2) is used to focus the beams into the sample, while its back focal plane is filled by a scanning telescope. For a larger FOV and the possibility to acquire 3D images, the sample is mounted on a motorized xyz-stage. The CRS signals are collected in the forward direction through a condenser lens (Olympus U-AAC, NA = 1.4). The CARS signal is isolated from the excitation laser wavelengths by a dichroic mirror (Semrock LP02-785RU) and a filter set (Semrock BSP01-785R x2, FF01-655/40-25) and finally detected by a photomultiplier tube (Hamamatsu Photonics H9656-20). The pump beam is separated by the same dichroic mirror and a filter (Semrock FF01-855/210-25, FF01-950/SP), and focused onto a Si photodiode (APE Berlin), which is fed into a fast lock-in amplifier (LIA, customized from APE Berlin) in combination to the reference modulation frequency delivered by the function generator. All resulting electronic signals are acquired by a data acquisition card (National Instruments PCI-6110S) and analyzed by the MATLAB program ScanImage (Version 3.8.1)⁶⁵. The scheme providing fast intensity modulation on the Stokes beam is achieved in the following way: a system trigger signal is generated from a leaked beam by using an InGaAs-photodiode (Thorlabs DET01-CFC). This 80 MHz pulse signal is then passed through an amplifier and a frequency divider, which divides the frequency by a factor of 4. This signal then

triggers a function generator (HP 8116A) that generates a 20 MHz sinusoidal frequency which is finally fed to the fast fiber-based intensity modulator (iXblue NIR-MX-LN-10) in the Stokes beam path. The synchronized trigger output of the function generator is used as the reference signal for the fast LIA.

Image processing. Images were processed with the open-source program ‘Fiji’. Here, we used the standard look-up-table “Cyan Hot” for the CARS images and “Red Hot” for the SRS images, as well as “red”, “green” and “magenta” for two-photon and SHG imaging. The black and white values were arbitrarily chosen for optimal contrast. The enlarged overview images of the mouse tissue were constructed from the raw data utilizing the plugin “Stitching” in Fiji.

Sample preparation. 1) Cultivation of cells: human bone osteosarcoma epithelial cells (U2OS) were cultured in Dulbecco’s modified Eagle’s medium (DMEM, Thermo Fisher) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Thermo Fisher) and Penicilium-Streptomycin (P/S, Sigma Aldrich) on a standard petri dish. Differentiating primary myoblast cells were cultivated in DMEM containing 5% horse serum (Thermo Fisher) and P/S on petri dishes coated with an extracellular matrix (Sigma Aldrich) at 1:500. All cells were cultured in a humidified incubator at 37°C, 5% O₂ and 5% CO₂. Before imaging, the cell medium was replaced by phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, Sigma Aldrich). 2) Tissue samples: the mouse superior vena cava tissue cryo-section was extracted from a 2-month old immunodeficiency mouse. The tissue was embedded in paraffin and cut into 50 μm thick sections with a cryo microtome; the mouse tail section was harvested from a C57BL/6 mouse around 3-month old, housed and maintained in the Animal and Plant Care Facility, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST). All animal experiments were approved by the HKUST Animal Ethics Committee; the mouse kidney section was ordered from Thermo Fisher Scientific (FluoCells® prepared slide #3); one-month old

Thy1-YFP H line mice were perfused with 4% paraformaldehyde. Brain tissue was taken out and post-fixed overnight. The brain tissue was further cut into 200 μm thick sections by a vibratome for two-photon imaging. Each cut was collected on a glass coverslip (No 1.5, Carl Roth) and stored in PBS. All experiments in these samples were approved and performed in accordance with The University of Hong Kong Committee on the Use of Live Animals in Teaching and Research guidelines.

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Author contributions

X.W., K.K.Y.W. and T.H. conceived the idea. X.W. and C.K. designed the two-color pulsed fiber laser system. C.K., C.P. and H.H. built and characterized the laser system. C.K., C.P. and H.H. built the laser scanning microscope, and performed the imaging experiments, C.P. and H.H.

analyzed the imaging data. T.H.C., C.S.W.L. and N.P.L. prepared the biological samples. K.K.T., K.K.Y.W. and T.H. obtained funding for this research. All authors wrote the manuscript and commented on it.

Competing financial interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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Figure 1 | Self-synchronized two-color pulsed fiber laser for multimodal nonlinear optical microscopy. **a.** Schematic diagram of the two-color pulsed fiber laser. A passively mode-locked fiber laser at 1.0 μm generates an fs pulse train at a repetition rate of 80 MHz. Its output is split into two branches by a fiber optic coupler (OC), respectively, for generating the Stokes and pump beams. After spatially combining Stokes and pump beams by a dichroic mirror (DM) and temporally overlapping them by a delay line (DL), the two-color laser beams are launched into a custom-built laser scanning microscope. The detailed description of the experimental setup is provided in **Supplementary Material 2**. DC-EDFA: double-cladding erbium/ytterbium-doped fiber amplifier. DC-YDFA: double-cladding ytterbium-doped fiber amplifier. Er: erbium-doped fiber. F: filter. FC: fiber collimator. FIM: fiber-coupled intensity modulator. G: grating. GVD: group velocity dispersion. L: lens. M: mirror. N_{rt} : round-trip number. OIM: fiber-based optically integrated module. PBS: polarizing beam splitter. PC: polarization controller. PD: photodiode. PPLN: periodically poled lithium niobate crystal. SMF: single-mode fiber. WDM: wavelength-division multiplexing coupler. XPM: cross-phase modulation. Yb: ytterbium-doped fiber. YDFA: ytterbium-doped fiber amplifier. $\lambda/2$: half-wave plate. $\lambda/4$: quarter-wave plate. **b-e.** Numerical simulations of the timing of 1.0 ps pulses at 1.5 μm without (**b,d**) and with (**c,e**) self-synchronization, respectively. The simulation assumes that the 1.5 μm pulses have an initial round-trip time mismatch of 50 fs, either slower (**b,c**) or faster (**d,e**). Further details are provided in **Supplementary Material 3**.

Figure 2 | Spectral characteristics of the two-color pulsed fiber laser. **a.** Coarse tuning range of the passively mode-locked fiber laser at 1.0 μm , tuned by the intracavity filter (F1, ~ 8.0 nm passband). **b.** Fine tuning range of the Stokes beam, 1010 – 1060 nm, tuned by the slit in the pulse compressor, i.e., the black dotted rectangle in **Fig. 1a**, which has an effective passband of ~ 1.0 nm. **c.** Tuning range of the coherent wavelength generator at 1.5 μm , tuned by the intracavity filter (F2, < 1.0 nm passband). **d.** Typical SHG spectrum centered at 789 nm, i.e., the pump beam. It is noted that the intensities of all figures have been normalized. **e.** SRS spectra of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and methanol samples in comparison to their spontaneous Raman (SR) spectra. Please note that, the spectra of DMSO has been vertically offset for better visualization.

Figure 3 | Temporal characteristics of the two-color pulsed fiber laser. **a.** Real-time pulse trains of the Stokes and pump beams at 1017 nm and 789 nm, respectively, recorded by a 20 GHz real-time oscilloscope. Extended pulse trains (up to 500 μ s) of the Stokes and pump beams are also provided in **Fig. S6**, which details the exceptionally low intensity noise of this two-color pulsed fiber laser. **b.** Real-time pulse train of the Stokes beam modulated by a 20 MHz sinusoidal function. The modulation depth is higher than 99%. **c.** Autocorrelation traces of the pump and Stokes beams and the pulse width stability of the Stokes beam over the tuning range. **d.** Long-term power stability over 100 minutes of both pump and Stokes beams. In this measurement, the output powers of the pump (789 nm) and Stokes (1017 nm) beams were set to \sim 100 mW and \sim 550 mW, respectively. Their root-mean-square (RMS) power fluctuations are only 0.1% and 0.5%, respectively. **e.** Optical cross-correlation measurement through sum-frequency generation (SFG). Gray and black curves show the monitored SFG intensities at the peak and half maximum of the optical cross-correlation trace (blue). **f.** Relative intensity noise (RIN) spectra of the two-color pulsed fiber laser, compared with a standard solid-state fs laser (Spectra-Physics MaiTai) and a typical supercontinuum (SC) fiber laser.

Figure 4 | CARS and SRS images of living human cells. **a,b.** CARS and SRS images of living osteosarcoma (U2OS) cells acquired simultaneously. The focal power was set to 33 mW and 74 mW for pump and Stokes beams, respectively. The pixel dwell time is 12.5 μs , while using 2 μs as the time constant for the lock-in amplifier. **c,d.** CARS and SRS images of living differentiating primary myoblast (PMD). 2x zoom-in was applied in order to reveal more details of the cells. Here, the focal power is 25 mW and 47 mW for pump and Stokes beams, respectively, while the pixel dwell time is 51.2 μs with a lock-in time constant of 20 μs . The arrows indicate the position of select lipid droplets inside the cells.

Figure 5 | CARS and SRS images of a mouse superior vena cava tissue cryo-section. **a.** Bright-field image of the mouse superior vena cava tissue cryo-section. The green and red regions of interest (ROIs) indicate the positions where CRS imaging was applied, respectively, and the violet dotted line displays the general location of the superior vena cava. **b,c.** CARS and SRS data, respectively, acquired from the red outlined area. Here we can discriminate between tunica media and tunica intima with excellent contrast, and visualize a thrombus containing red blood cells, see yellow inset of **b**, which adhere to the arterial wall. A pink dotted line is inserted in **b** to depict the elastica interna, separating both areas from each other. **d,e.** CARS and SRS images of the green outlined area detailing the lipid rich tunica media of the superior vena cava. The optical power was set to 33 mW and 74 mW for pump and Stokes beams, respectively. The pixel dwell time is 6.4 μs , in combination with a lock-in time constant of 2 μs . The modulation frequency of the Stokes beam is 20 MHz. **f.** Corresponding line scans of images **d** and **e**, the location is indicated by the green line in image **e**. Here, we compare CARS and SRS signal at a lipid rich area of the tunica media. Small lipid regions are revealed by SRS due to its enhanced chemical sensitivity (red arrows). The signal was normalized to the highest signal intensity of both channels, respectively.

Figure 6 | SHG imaging of a mouse tail sample and two-photon fluorescence imaging of kidney and brain tissue sections. **a.** SHG image of a non-stained mouse tail slide. The applied polarization was controlled by a half-wave plate and a quarter-wave plate. A focal power of ~ 20 mW was applied to the sample utilizing the FCPA output of the Stokes beam (bandwidth ~ 8 nm, pulse width ~ 200 fs). **b,c.** Two-photon excited fluorescence images of mouse kidney section (Thermo Fisher Scientific FluoCells® prepared slide #3), using a focal power of ~ 20 mW. **d,e.** Two-photon excited fluorescence images of 200- μm thick mouse brain tissue sample prepared between two glass slides where the mouse expresses the yellow fluorescent protein (YFP) in layer-V pyramidal neurons (Thy1-YFP H-line)⁵⁹. **d** shows a 3D-volume composition of data acquired via z-scanning over 145 μm (montage made with Fiji volume viewer) while **e** is a single frame illustrating the neuron distribution. Here, a focal power of ~ 50 mW was applied.

Table 1. Performance of all-fiber lasers enabling SRS imaging

Fiber laser sources	Current work	ASFL ¹⁸	SSFSFL ²⁹	SCFL ³²
Synchronization scheme	Passive	Active	Passive	Passive
Power [pump, Stokes], mW	[160, 1000]	[12, 15]	[120, 10]	[75, 120]
Long-term power stability, %	<0.5	/	/	/
RIN [pump, Stokes], dBc/Hz	[-147, -148]	/	/	~[-140, -90] [*]
Pulse width [pump, Stokes], ps	[2.7, 3.2]	[4, 3]	~[0.7, 0.47±0.11]	[4.0, 1.0]
Pulse width variation, %	<1.8%	/	~25	/
Wavenumber region, cm⁻¹	2700–3550	2600–3411	2330–3330	2670–3630
Timing jitter, fs	24.3	227	/	<24
Intensity modulation depth, %	>99	/	/	/
SRS imaging speed, μs/pixel	6.4	3000 ^{**}	3000 ^{**}	<5 ^{**}
<p>[*]The RIN of the Stokes beam is not provided in the reference, and here it was estimated from the results of duplicated experiments (Fig. 3f). Noted that, a better value could have been obtained in the reference. ^{**}The SRS imaging was performed with additional balanced detection for suppressing the intensity noise.</p>				